

Experimental Study of the Injectability and Effectiveness of Laponite Mixtures as Liquefaction Mitigation Technique

Lucia Mele, Ph.D. student,¹ Alessandro Flora, Ph.D.,² Stefania Lirer, Ph.D.,³ Anna d'Onofrio, Ph.D.⁴, Emilio Bilotta, Ph.D.⁵

¹University of Napoli Federico II, Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering, Via Claudio 21 –Napoli 80125; e-mail: lucia.mele@unina.it

²University of Napoli Federico II, Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering, Via Claudio 21 –Napoli 80125; e-mail: flora@unina.it

³University of Guglielmo Marconi, Department of Engineering of Sustainability, Via Plinio 44 – Roma 00193; e-mail: s.lirer@unimarconi.it

⁴University of Napoli Federico II, Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering, Via Claudio 21 –Napoli 80125; e-mail: anna.donofrio@unina.it

⁵University of Napoli Federico II, Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering, Via Claudio 21 –Napoli 80125; e-mail: emilio.bilotta@unina.it

ABSTRACT

The recent earthquakes that hit Italy have shown that the built heritage is at risk not only because of inertial and kinematic stresses directly induced on the structure by shaking, but also because of possible soil liquefaction phenomena. The techniques generally used to mitigate the soil liquefaction susceptibility in the case of new constructions (vibro-compaction, dynamic compaction, etc.), are generally not suitable for existing buildings. Within a large European project (LIQUEFACT), the University of Napoli is studying innovative soil improvement techniques suitable for the mitigation of the soil liquefaction risk in densely urbanized areas. In this paper, the addition of fine content (laponite) is experimentally studied by means of different preliminary laboratory tests with the main goal to verify the injectability and effectiveness of the selected mixtures against liquefaction. The applicability of this technique has been verified by means of viscosity and permeability tests, while its effectiveness has been analyzed via cyclic triaxial tests. Experimental results show that the addition of an additive (SPP) to delay the mixture gelling time is necessary to assure the injectability of the tested laponite mixtures. The addition of fine content reduces the mobility of grains and modifies the pore pressure building up during cycling loads, leading to an increase of soil liquefaction resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Liquefaction is a well-known phenomenon in which the stiffness and the strength of saturated loose granular soils are suddenly reduced by seismic activity. During a seismic load the effective stresses of the soil approach to zero and it behaves temporarily as a viscous liquid. It is well-known that the relative density (D_r) of the soil is the key parameter that rules the triggering of the liquefaction phenomenon (Ishihara 1985): for such a reason, the most used liquefaction mitigation techniques are those that induce a soil densification (for instance, by vibro-compaction or dynamic compaction). These kind of techniques cannot be applied in densely urbanized areas or sites with historic buildings to be preserved. In these cases, it becomes necessary to adopt less invasive mitigation techniques that combine the need to reduce the risk of liquefaction and the protection of the integrity of the existing buildings. The low pressure grouting, that consists in the injection of mixtures within the soil pores without modify the soil structure, is particularly suitable for these conditions.

Many experimental studies (Ishihara and Koseki 1989; Seed et al. 1983; Tokimatsu and Yoshimi 1983; Ishihara 1993) have shown that the use of mixtures of controlled quantities of highly plastic particles, can increase the soil liquefaction resistance. El Mohtar et al. 2014 have used bentonite and laponite as plastic particles. In the case of laponite, even in small percentages (1-5% of the dry weight of the soil), the effectiveness of the treatment can be due to two mechanisms: the creation of "bridges" between sand grains due to the plastic nature of laponite, and the formation within the pores of a gel-like fluid that behaves as a material with a small distortion-stiffness (Huang et al. 2016; Ochoa-Cornejo et al. 2016). Both mechanisms reduce the mobility of sand grains during loading cycles, improving the liquefaction resistance.

In low pressure grouting, the most important aspect to analyze is the injectability of the mixture that is strongly related to its initial viscosity (μ) and its variation over time $\mu(t)$. The chemical composition of the mixture must be calibrated (also by adding additives) in order to guarantee that the injection time is less than the gelling time of the mixture, because it marks a large increase in viscosity and hence a considerable slowing down of the permeation process.

The article shows the preliminary results of an experimental research developed at the University of Napoli Federico II with the aim to analyze the injectability of laponite mixtures in sand and the effect of such treatment on the reduction of the liquefaction potential of soil.

EXPERIMENTAL ACTIVITY

Tested materials

The experimental research was carried out on a monogranular sand (Leighton Buzzard fraction E), characterized by a specific gravity G_s of 2.65 and a minimum and maximum void ratios (e_{min} and e_{max}) of 0.613 and 1.014 respectively. The mechanical behavior of the Leighton Buzzard sand was deeply investigated in previous studies (Visone 2008; Lanzano et al. 2016).

In the experimental program, laponite RD ($Na^{+0.7} [(Si_8Mg_{5.5}Li_{0.3}) O_{20} (OH)_4]^{-0.7}$) was adopted. Laponite is a colloidal clay consisting essentially of a mixture of sodium and magnesium silicates, with a structure similar to the montmorillonite one. The particle of laponite has a disk

shape with a diameter of 25 nm, thickness of 1 nm and specific gravity $G_s = 2.57$ (Rockwood Additives Ltd. 2011). The plasticity index PI is very high: 1100%, and for this reason it is called "super-plastic nanoparticle" (El Howayek 2011). Laponite particles have numerous negative charges on their surface, which are nominally related to sodium (or magnesium) as a counterion (Huang and Wang 2016). In Figure 1 the phase diagram of laponite is shown. It represents the ionic strength of the mixture (concentration of ions in solution in terms of molar concentration M) with the concentration of laponite in water, ϕ (ratio between the mass of laponite with the mass of water). When laponite is dissolved in water the phase of the mixture is Liquid (section A of Fig. 1) with a viscosity similar to that of water (1 cP). When laponite hydrates and swells the viscosity increases, forming a gel (Sol phase, section B in Fig. 1). The Sol phase (point B) represents the passage between a strongly aqueous solution and an Attractive gel (point C). If the percentage of laponite increases over time, for example in the case of drying, a solid phase similar to a vitrification process occurs, it is divided into Attractive and Repulsive Glass (D and E points respectively).

The concentration of laponite therefore regulates the state (liquid, gel or solid) of the mixture: during the permeation process, in which the aqueous mixture of laponite must permeate without altering the soil structure, the mixture must be in a liquid phase. After the permeation process, a phase transition occurs and a new gel-like structure can be identified for the laponite mixture.

Figure 1. Phase diagram of laponite RD (adapted by Santagata 2014): ionic strength versus the concentration of laponite in water ϕ .

Viscosity and permeability tests

The injectability of a mixture within the pores of a soil (Lirer et al. 2006) is related to the size of the suspended particles, the initial viscosity of the mixture (μ_0), and its gelling time, t_{gel} (time when its viscosity increases significantly). These rheological parameters can be measured by

means of viscosity tests with a Marsh cone: the tests were carried out on water/laponite mixtures prepared with two different concentrations ϕ ($\phi = 1.5 - 3.0\%$, Tab. 1). In two tests (PV3 and PV4), an additive (SPP = sodium pyrophosphate) was also added to the water/laponite mixture in order to test its influence on rheological mixture properties. The tested mixtures were made by mixing dry laponite (and SPP in PV3 and PV4) with water, always ensuring a complete solubilization of the components.

The results of the viscosity tests (Fig.2a) show that the initial value of the viscosity (μ) of the tested mixtures is very low and similar to that of the water ($\mu_w=1\text{cP}$), except for the test PV2 and it is due to its higher concentration. The results indicate that initial viscosity and the gelling time (t_{gel}) of the mixtures without additives (PV1 and PV2) are obviously a function of the concentration of laponite. As expected, the additive (SPP) ensures low viscosity of the mixture even in the presence of high concentration ($\phi = 3\%$), and delays the gelification process of the mixture, favoring in situ mixture injection.

Table 1. Viscosity and permeability tests.

	Test	Fluid	Lap ϕ (%)	SPP (%)
Viscosity tests	PW	water	-	-
	PV1	water+lap	1.5	-
	PV2	water+lap	3	-
	PV3	water+lap+SPP	3	0.06
	PV4	water+lap+SPP	3	0.03
Permeability tests	PL1	water+lap	1.5	-
	PL2	water+lap	3	-
	PL3	water+lap+SPP	3	0.06
	PL4	water+lap+SPP	3	0.03

The constant load permeability tests (Tab.1) were carried out in a permeameter (diameter $d= 35.3$ mm and a height $h=72$ mm) with the aim to measure the permeability of the sand specimens ($Dr_0 = 40\%$) to the water (k_w), to the water/laponite mixture and finally to the water/laponite/SPP mixtures. The permeability coefficient measured in the PW test is $k_w=2.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m/s and can be considered as a reference value.

In Figure 2b, the results of the tests carried out with water/laponite/SPP mixtures are shown: it can be observed that the permeability coefficient k_m measured for both tests was very similar to k_w . In the same figure are also plotted the values of k_m calculated by means of the well-known relationship:

$$k_m = \frac{\mu_w}{\mu_m} \cdot \frac{\gamma_m}{\gamma_w} \cdot k_w \quad (1)$$

where μ_w and μ_m represent the initial viscosity of the water and the mixture respectively, while γ_w and γ_m are the specific weights of the water and the mixture water/laponite ($\gamma_m = 10.3$ kN/m³). It can be noted that, until the viscosity of the mixture μ_m remains low, there is a very good agreement among the calculated and measured values of k_m . When the mixture viscosity begins

to increase, the permeability values calculated by the eq. 1 begin to decrease and moves away from the measured values. This result indicates that during the permeability test the gelling time of the mixture is greater than that measured during the viscosity test. This may be due to the fact that in the permeability test the mixture is in motion, contrary to what happens in the Marsh cone. The continuous movement of the mixture can cause a delay of gelling time.

Figure 2. Viscosity (a) and permeability (b) tests.

During the permeability tests the permeated mixture was collected to evaluate the concentration of laponite in water. The results of PL3 and PL4 tests were plotted in figure 3. In both cases, ϕ is null at the beginning of the permeation because of the pore water going out from the specimen, after that ϕ increases until to reach a value of 3%, which corresponds to the initial concentration of laponite of the prepared mixture.

Figure 1. Concentration of laponite in the permeated mixture measured during the tests PL3 and PL4.

Cyclic triaxial tests

The sand liquefaction resistance has been studied by means of undrained cyclic triaxial tests performed in a Bishop & Wesley triaxial apparatus. Nine tests (S1-S9, Tab. 2) have been carried out on untreated sandy specimens and other two tests (SL1 and SL2, Tab.2) on sand-laponite specimens. Sandy specimens were reconstituted (wet pluviation) with an initial relative density $Dr_0 = 40\%$ and frozen: the freezing was necessary because the double drainage of the apparatus doesn't allow the application of the vacuum.

Table 2. Cyclic triaxial tests.

Test	Fine (%)	D_r^* (%)	Aging (h)	σ'_c (kPa)	CRR	N_{liq}
S1	-	47	1	25	0.115	12
S2	-	45	1	50	0.179	1.2
S3	-	55	1	50	0.128	12
S4	-	50	1	50	0.080	No
S5	-	47	1	50	0.109	14
S6	-	52	1	50	0.097	No
S7	-	55	1	50	0.147	4
S8	-	44	1	100	0.099	33
S9	-	45	1	100	0.197	1.1
SL1	1	53	110	50	0.135	38
SL2	1	57	110	50	0.162	6.1

**after consolidation phase*

The sand-laponite specimens were made by manually mixing sand and dry laponite: the amount of laponite added in the specimen is 1% of dry weight of sand. The sand/laponite mixture was subsequently wet pluviated (the corresponding concentration of laponite is $\phi = 3\%$) in a steel cylinder and then frozen.

The frozen specimen was subjected to a thawing phase into the triaxial cell in drained condition, by applying an effective confining stress $\sigma'_c = 5$ kPa. After thawing, the specimen was isotropically consolidated at different values of confining stress ($\sigma'_c = 25-50-100$ kPa, Tab.2). The time between the end of consolidation and the beginning of the deviatoric phase is the *aging time*. This time is equal to one hour for untreated specimens, and 110 hours for the sand-laponite specimens (Tab.2): this longer time ensures the complete gelification of laponite within the pores. After the aging time, a cyclic deviatoric stress q_d , was applied while keeping constant the value of the cell stress. Different values of the cyclic stress ratio CSR ($CSR = q_d / 2 \cdot \sigma'_c$) were applied and the pore pressure ratio R_u (defined as the ratio between the water pressure increment Δu that develops during test and the applied consolidation stress σ'_c) was computed during the cycles (N_{cyc}). As well known, the attainment of liquefaction can be conventionally defined either in terms of measured pore pressure increments Δu (typically assuming that the soil liquefies when the pore pressure ratio $R_u \geq 0.9$, where $R_u = \Delta u / \sigma'_c$), or in terms of axial strain (typically assuming that the soil liquefies when $\epsilon_{DA} \geq 5\%$, where ϵ_{DA} is the double amplitude axial strain). In

this research, the pore pressure ratio R_u has been chosen as criterion for liquefaction attainment. Some results of the cyclic triaxial test S3 carried out on natural specimen and of the test SL1 on sand-laponite specimen, are plotted (Fig. 4) in the two traditional planes: deviatoric stress q versus effective mean stress p' and cyclic stress ratio CSR – number of cycles N_{cyc} – pore pressure ratio R_u . For both tests it can be observed that - in the q - p' plane (Fig.4 a, c) – during the cycles the stress paths move to the origin of the axes: in the test S3, the stress path touches the failure envelope ($M_{comp}=1.35$, $M_{ext} = -0.88$, Visone 2008). It can be noted that even though the two tests were carried out with a similar value of CSR (CSR= 0.128 for S3 test, CSR= 0.135 for SL1 test), for the sand-laponite specimen the liquefaction occurs after a larger number of cycles ($N_{liq}(S3) = 12$; $N_{liq}(SL1) = 38$). Such result is highlighted in the Figure 5, where the results of both tests are plotted in terms of pore pressure increments Δu measured during the cyclic loading phases: for the sand-laponite specimen a delay in the build-up of the pore pressure is clearly evident. The delay in the building up of pore pressures can be explained by a reduction of the sand grains mobility, due to the presence of the gel-like phase of the fluid of porosity, given by the addition of the nano-particles of laponite.

Figure 2. Results of cyclic tests S3 (a,b) and SL1 (c,d).

Figure 3. Excess pore pressure versus N_{cyc} .

The results of the cyclic triaxial tests are summarized in the traditional cyclic resistance plane $CRR-N_{liq}$, where CRR is the cyclic resistance ratio defines as the cyclic stress ratio that causes liquefaction in a finite number of loading cycles and N_{liq} is the number of cycles to initiate liquefaction (Fig. 6). It can be observed that the cyclic resistance curve (for a confining stress $\sigma'_c = 50$ kPa) of sand-laponite specimens is higher than the one obtained for the untreated sand specimens. This confirms again how a very small amount of plastic nano-particles (in these tests equal to 1%) of laponite has a very important influence on the sand behavior under cyclic loading paths. Other tests on sand-laponite specimens are under course in order to add other experimental point to better identify the cyclic resistance curve for the treated sand.

Figure 4. Cyclic resistance curves.

CONCLUSION

The results of different viscosity and permeability tests carried out on some laponite mixtures have shown that due to their low initial viscosity (comparable to that of water), such mixtures can permeate within the pores of the soil without altering its structure. The results of cyclic triaxial tests have also confirmed that small amount of laponite (1% of dry weight of sand) can increase the soil liquefaction strength: the presence of a laponite gel within the pores limits the mobility of sand grains and thus delays the triggering of the liquefaction process. The experimental research is still ongoing and other tests will be carried out in order to analyze the rule of other parameters (confining stresses, additives, laponite contents) on the complex mechanisms of interaction between the porous fluid and the soil grain, responsible for the liquefaction phenomenon.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper is written within the European Project LIQUEFACT. LIQUEFACT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 700748.

The authors thank to Dr. Letizia Verdolotti and CNR-IPCB for the support on chemical aspects of the research.

REFERENCES

- El Howayek A., (2011). “Characterization, rheology and microstructure of laponite suspension”. *MS Thesis*, School of Civil Eng., Purdue University.
- El Mohtar C.S., Bobet A., Drnevich V.P., Johnston C.T., Santagata M.C., (2014). “Pore pressure generation in sand with bentonite: from small strains to liquefaction”. *Géotechnique*, 64 (2), 108-107.
- Huang Y. e Wang L., (2016). “Laboratory investigation of liquefaction mitigation in silty sand using laponite”. *Engineering Geology*, 204, 23-32.
- Ishihara K., (1985). “Stability of Natural Deposits during Earthquakes”, *Proc. of the 11th Int. Conf. on Soil Mech. and Found. Eng.*, 1, San Francisco, 321-376.
- Ishihara K. and Koseki J., (1989). “Discussion of cyclic shear strength of fines-containing sands”. *Proc., 12th Int. Conf. on Soil Mech. Geotech. Eng.*, London, 101-106.
- Ishihara K., (1993). “Liquefaction and flow failure during earthquakes”. *Géotechnique*, 43 (3), 351-415.

- Lanzano G., Visone C., Bilotta E., Santucci de Magistris F. (2016). "Experimental assessment of the stress–strain behaviour of Leighton Buzzard sand for the calibration of a constitutive model". *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, 34:991–1012.
- Lirer S., Flora A., Verdolotti L., Lavorgna M., Iannace S., (2006). "Permeation grouting of fine grained pyroclastic soils and rocks". *Ground Improvement*, 10: 135-177.
- Ochoa-Cornejo F., Bobet A., Johnston C. T., Santagata M., Sinfield J. V., (2016). "Cyclic behaviour and pore pressure generation in sands with laponite, a super-plastic nanoparticle". *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 88, 265-279.
- Rockwood Additives Ltd. (2011). Laponite performance additives. Specification sheet.
- Santagata M., Bobet A., El Howayek A., Ochoa-Cornejo F., Sinfield J.V., Johnston C.T., (2014). "Building a nanostructure in the pore fluid of granular soils". In: Soga K., Kumar K., Biscontin G., Kuo M. (eds.) *Geomechanics from Micro Macro*. 1377-1383.
- Seed H. B., Idriss I.M., Arango I., (1983). "Evaluation of liquefaction potential using field performance data". *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, 109 (3), 458-482.
- Tokimatsu K. and Yoshimi Y., (1983). "Empirical correlation of soil liquefaction based on SPT N-value and fines content". *Soils and Foundations*, 23 (4), 56-74.
- Visone C., (2008). "Performance-based approach in seismic design of embedded retaining walls". *PhD Thesis*, University of Napoli Federico II, Napoli, Italy.